

Chemical Examination of *Tephrosia purpurea* Linn Seeds

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T. purpurea Linn oil consists of palmitic, palmitoleic, stearic, oleic, linoleic and linolenic acids in the weight ratio of 38.5, 4.5, 9.4, 45.0, 2.1 and 0.5 percent. Techniques of chromatography revealed the presence of eighteen amino acids. Quantitation of amino acids by two different methods gave comparable results for all amino acids except alanine and methionine. Essential amino acid make-up is as follows:—lysine (8.5), histidine (1.74), threonine (8.03), valine (2.36), phenylalanine + tyrosine (10.10), methionine + cystine (0.48) and leucine + isoleucine (8.91) percent. The proteins are deficient in tryptophane and methionine.

T. PURPUREA Linn, a wild legume of the family "Papilionaceae", is distributed throughout India. Earlier workers studied its glycosides^{1,2} and fatty acid composition³ by conventional methods of analysis. Because of little published information on the subject, its calorie, nutritional characteristics of the oil and proteins were investigated chromatographically and reported in this communication.

Experimental

The seeds of *T. purpurea* Linn were exhausted with petroleum ether (B. P. 60-80°) and a yellowish brown oil obtained in yield 10.6%. Calorie contents, proximate chemical composition of the legume and physicochemical characteristics of the extracted oil were determined by standard methods. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF LEGUME AND OIL

	I*	II*
Moisture % in seeds	3.15	—
Oil %	10.6	11.3
Protein %	34.54	—
Total sugars	45.3	—
Calorie contents	485.2 cal/100 gm.	—
Ash	3.45	—
Specific gravity of oil at 30°C	0.9221	0.928
Refractive Index at 30°C	1.4725	1.428
Saponification value	176.2	172.5
Iodine value (Hanus method)	75.4	101.4
Acid value	0.38	2.6
Unsaponifiable matter %	3.2	9.5

* Data of present investigations.

potassium hydroxamates for chromatographic investigations. Fatty acids, their methyl esters and hydroxamates were chromatographed by reversed phase chromatography⁴⁻⁷ on liquid paraffin impregnated Whatman filter paper No. 1 and cellulose TLC plates with 85% glacial acetic acid as solvent using usual staining reagents. Methyl esters and hydroxamic acids were resolved by argentation TLC on 12% silver nitrate impregnated silica gel G-plates using petroleum ether : ether (9 : 1) as solvent. The spots were detected by charring technique. Gas liquid chromatography of methyl esters was carried out in an F & M Model 720 Gas Chromatograph provided with a thermal conductivity detector, using DEGS-15% (Polyester of diethylene glycol succinate) as the stationary phase and nitrogen as carrier gas. The temperatures of the column, injection part and detector block were 210, 300 and 300° respectively. Six clear peaks of the GLC Curve were quantitated by peak area method. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF OIL

S. No.	Component Acids	Percentage by weight	
		I*	II*
1.	Palmitic	38.5	23.2
2.	Stearic	9.4	—
3.	Palmitoleic	4.5	—
4.	Oleic	45.0	43.6
5.	Linoleic	2.1	30.8
6.	Linolenic	0.5	2.4

* Data of present investigations.

Analysis of oil :

The oil was hydrolysed and mixed acids were isolated and transformed into methyl esters and

Analysis of proteins :

Proteins were extracted in yield 28.6% from the defatted seeds with alkaline 10% brine solution and

the isolate was hydrolysed⁸. Protein hydrolysate dissolved in 10% isopropanol was chromatographed by various techniques of paper (Whatman No. 1) and cellulose (MN. 300) thin layer chromatography⁹⁻¹⁵ using (1) n-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 1.6); (2) Pyridine : water (4 : 1); (3) n-butanol : pyridine : water (1 : 1 : 1) and (4) phenol : water (3 : 1) as solvents and various specific and multiple spraying reagents¹⁶⁻¹⁷. Butanol-acetic acid-water, in combination with pyridine-water/butanol-pyridine-water/phenol-water were used as solvents for developing two dimensional chromatograms. Amino acids were also resolved on MN Ionex-25 SA-Na cation exchange thin layer chromatography plates¹⁸ using 3.2 pH citrate buffer as solvent by ascending run technique. Ninhydrin colours of individual amino acids of the two dimensionally developed chromatograms were estimated photometrically¹⁹ at 570 nm using a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20-colorimeter. Amino acids were also quantitated using Perkin-Elmer KLA-3B-automatic amino acid analyser. The results are given in Table 3.

supported by six methyl ester peaks of the GLC-curve. Quantitation by peak area method revealed the presence of palmitic, palmitoleic, stearic, oleic, linolic and linolenic acids in the weight ratio of 38.5, 4.5, 9.4, 45.0, 2.1 and 0.5 percent in the oil of *T. purpurea* Linn seeds. Presence of palmitoleic acid is reported for the first time. Contrary to earlier report, the oil has been found to be poor in polyunsaturated fatty acids. Two dimensional paper, cellulose and ion exchange resin thin layer chromatography revealed the presence of eighteen amino acids including eight of essential and five of semi essential type. Quantitation by two dimensional chromatography combined with photometric determination of ninhydrin colours gave results comparable to those obtained by using automatic amino acid analyser for all amino acids except alanine and methionine. The seed proteins are particularly rich in lysine, phenylalanine+tyrosine and threonine. Tryptophane and methionine appear to be its limiting amino acids. The seeds also contain sufficient calorie.

TABLE 3—AMINO ACID COMPOSITION OF PROTEIN ISOLATE

(Amino acid percentage expressed in g/16g of nitrogen)			
S. No.	% of Amino acid	I†	II*
Indispensable			
1.	Lysine	8.32	8.10
2.	Histidine	1.82	1.74
3.	Threonine	7.41	8.08
4.	Phenylalanine	6.29	6.42
5.	Valine	2.13	2.36
6.	Methionine	—	0.48
7.	Leucine and isoleucine	8.19	8.91
Semi-Indispensable			
8.	Serine	8.29	8.62
9.	Glycine	4.96	5.36
10.	Tyrosine	3.46	3.68
11.	Cystine	—	Traces
12.	Arginine	14.65	14.86
Dispensable			
13.	Glutamic acid	30.40	14.36
14.	Aspartic acid	—	16.44
15.	Alanine	1.03	6.43
16.	Proline	—	Traces
17.	γ-Aminobutyric acid	—	Traces

† Data of automatic amino acid analyser

Results and Discussion

Presence of usual fatty acids is revealed by reversed phase paper and cellulose TLC methods. Fatty acids, their methyl esters and hydroxamic acids possess identical separation sequence. Argentation TLC of methyl esters and hydroxamic acids gave clear spots of the saturates, monoenes, dienes and trienes parallel to their authentic samples resolved along side. Observations of reversed phase paper, cellulose and argentation TLC, are further

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